

Determination of stability constants of metal-methionine and metal-methionine-NTA (binary and mixed) complexes by ionophoretic technique

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Abstract : Electrophoretic technique has been used for the study of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}-methionine binary and Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}-methionine-NTA (nitrilotriacetic acid) ternary complexes. The stability constants of metal-methionine binary complexes are found to be 10^{6.03}, 10^{5.23}, 10^{5.13}, 10^{4.23} and the stability constants of metal-methionine-NTA ternary complexes have been found to be 10^{6.35}, 10^{6.04}, 10^{5.87}, 10^{5.80} for Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (HClO₄) and 25 °C.

Keywords : Binary complex, ternary complex, stability constant, ionophoretic technique.

Introduction

It is well known that the sulphur containing amino acids are of biological importance. The significance of these amino acids is enhanced by the fact that they display independent therapeutic activity¹. In recent years they have been utilized in connection with rheumatoid arthritis and neonatal jaundice². Their biological importance is attributed to the capabilities of the mercapto group to undergo various complex formation processes. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are well known for their biomedical applications and toxicity³. In this communication, an attempt has been made to study the stability constants of mononuclear binary and ternary complexes formed in systems containing Fe^{III}/Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}/Co^{II}-methionine and Fe^{III}/Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}/Co^{II}-methionine-NTA. A simple electrophoretic tube described previously has been used for the work⁴.

Results and discussion

Metal-methionine binary system : Fig. 1 illustrates the relationship between 'absorbance' difference and the 'pH' and thus gives an idea of the change of overall mobility of the metal ion species with change in hydrogen ion concentration of the system containing Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and methionine. A curve with a number of plateaus indicates the formation of certain complex species. The first plateau in each case corresponds to a region of pH where metal ions are uncomplexed. In this low pH re-

gion, the concentration of the protonated form of methionine (CH₃SCH₂CH₂CH(NH₃⁺)COOH) is maximum. Further increase in pH leads to increase in ligating methionine anion concentration [L⁻] and brings about a progressive decrease in overall ionic mobility of the metal ion species. This decrease indicates formation of complex of the metal ion with the ligand. A point is reached beyond which mobility of the metal ion species remain constant regardless of the increase of pH of reaction mixture. This is the second plateau which corresponds to a pH region in which 1 : 1 complex is predominantly formed. One methionine anion combines with each metal ion to form [Fe(CH₃SCH₂CH₂CH(NH₂COO)]²⁺, [Cu-(CH₃SCH₂CH₂CH(NH₂)COO)]⁺, [Ni(CH₃SCH₂CH₂CH(NH₂)COO)]⁺ and [Co(CH₃SCH₂CH₂CH(NH₂)COO)]⁺ cationic complexes. Beyond this plateau, increase of pH has no effect and mobility remain constant. The overall mobility *U* is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by the following equation :

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + K_1 [L] + K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots} \quad (1)$$

where *K*'s are the stability constants of complexes and [L] is the concentration of methionine ion. *u*'s (*u*₀, *u*₁, *u*₂) are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be assessed from the plateaus of the

Fig. 1. Mobility curve. Metal-methionine systems.

figure. In the region between first and second plateau the system contains overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. The existence of 1 : 2 complex can be excluded and hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. U would be equal to $(u_0 + u_1)/2$ provided $K_1 [L] = 1$. Accordingly, the pH corresponding to the average value of u_0 and u_1 is found from the figure and with the knowledge of the dissociation constant of methionine ($pK_1 = 2.20$ and $pK_2 = 9.05$)⁵, the concentration of methionine ion at this pH is calculated. It's reciprocal gives the stability constant K of the 1 : 1 complex which are reported. The concentration of chelating methionine anion $[L^-]$ is determined as :

$$[L^-] = \frac{[L_T]}{1 + [H]/k_1 + [H]^2/k_1k_2} \quad (2)$$

where $[L_T]$ is the total concentration of the ligand methionine and k_1 and k_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of the methionine.

Metal-methionine-NTA ternary system : Fig. 2 depicts the observation of studies carried out in methionine-NTA ternary complexes. These graphs clearly show the formation of two plateaus in each cases. The first plateau corresponds to binary M-methionine complex whereas the second plateau corresponds to the formation of new com-

plex. This new complex may be mixed type complex of the type M-L-NTA or pure M-NTA complex. But with the help of related graphs of M-NTA complexes it was found that the absorbance difference in case of new complex is not identical to M-NTA pure complex. Further this ternary complex has greater mobility than that of binary M-methionine complex and hence these observations confirm the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed M-L-NTA complex as :

For M-L-NTA complexes the stability constant K' is calculated by using modified equation;

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1K'[NTA]}{1 + K'[NTA]} \quad (4)$$

Here u_0 and u_1 are the mobilities of M-L and M-L-NTA complexes respectively.

From the figures, concentration of NTA at which overall mobility is the mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus is determined. The concentration of NTA anion at pH 8.0 for this NTA concentration is calculated. K' is obviously equal to $1/[NTA]$. All these values are also reported and clearly indicates the superior coordinating power of NTA anion to other amino acid species.

Fig. 2. Mobility curve. Metal-methionine-NTA system.

The stability constant values for binary (M-L) and ternary (M-L-NTA) complexes are : Fe^{III} (6.03, 6.35) > Cu^{II} (5.23, 6.04) > Ni^{II} (5.13, 5.87) > Co^{II} (4.23, 5.80).

The stability constants of binary complexes in case of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are in quite good agreement with the literature values⁵. The variations in case of Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} can be attributed to difference in experimental conditions. The study of Cu^{II}-methionine and Co^{II}-methionine binary complexes by paper electrophoresis also confirms our finding⁶.

Experimental

Metal-methionine binary system : One set of 15 ml solution each containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}/Co^{II}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ methionine was prepared at different pH values (by adding NaOH solution). In case of Fe^{III}, $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe^{III}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ methionine was used. 10 ml of this solution is taken in an ionophoretic tube and then thermostated at 25 °C. The position of the tube was adjusted in such a way that the level of the solution in one wide end arm reached a circular mark on it. This adjustment fixed the volume of the solution on both sides of the middle stopper. Two (0.5 cm × 0.5 cm) platinum electrodes were dipped in each arm cup and a 50 V potential difference was applied be-

tween them. Electrolysis of the solution was allowed for 45 min, after which the middle stopper of the tube is closed. The solution of the anodic compartment was taken out in a 15 ml flask. The copper content of the solution was converted to copper thiocyanate⁷. The volume was raised to a mark in the flask and the absorbance at 408 nm was measured with CZ-specol spectrophotometer. The Co^{II} content of the anodic compartment was converted to cobalt thiocyanate⁷ complex and absorbance at 625 nm was measured. The Ni^{II} content was converted to nickel dimethylglyoximate and absorbance was taken at 445 nm⁸. Similarly the Fe^{III} content of the anodic compartment was converted to Fe thiocyanate complex and absorbance was measured at 480 nm against a reagent blank⁸. These observations are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

Metal-methionine-NTA ternary system : The study of ternary complexes was carried out by progressive addition of secondary ligand NTA from $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ at a fixed pH 8.0 to a mixture of metal ion (having same concentration as in binary systems), $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ methionine and 0.1 M perchloric acid. The reason behind keeping the reaction mixture at pH 8.0 is that much ahead of this pH the simple binary complexes of metal-methionine and M-NTA are formed and remain intact even beyond this pH⁹. The amount of secondary

Note

ligand NTA was increased each time in the electrophoretic tube and the electrolysis of the solution and its observations were recorded each time as it was done in case of binary complexes. These observations are graphically represented in Fig. 2.

A number of factors¹⁰ (e.g. diffusion, ionic strength and temperature) obviously vitiate the electrophoretic mobility of a particular ion. The technique described here is almost free of these vitiating factors and the reliability may vary to $\pm 2\%$. In the last, it is concluded that this simple and handy electrophoretic technique can be used as a strong tool for the study of metal-ligand interactions in binary and ternary complexes.

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